

THE REVIEW OF CORRUPTION ERADICATION IN INDONESIA BASED ON THE ASPECT OF JURIDICAL, MORALITY, AND IDEOLOGY OF PANCASILA

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Abstract

This article proposes to review the handling of corruption cases judicially, morality, and by the ideology of Pancasila in Indonesia. This study is normative legal research with descriptive analysis. This study uses the philosophical approach and the concept approach to find out efforts carried out by the government to tackle corruption in Indonesia from the juridical and moral aspects of the Indonesian people based on the Pancasila Ideology. The corruption eradication efforts have not been able to be resolved optimally because it is having been spread sporadically in Indonesia. Obstacles are on structural, cultural, instrumental and management aspects. The prevention and eradication of corruption must be emphasized as a moral responsibility of the Indonesian people. Because it will be one of the biggest threats to the existence of the Indonesian nation. Corruption prevention must be carried out systematically by strengthening regulations and conducting international cooperation in making the issue of corruption as a crime against Human Rights throughout the world, especially in Indonesia. The aspect of law enforcement in eradicating criminal acts of corruption requires the role of all parties involved in achieving the target in the eradication of corruption that have become an epidemic in Indonesia, there are four factors causing corruption; political and judicial factor, historical factor, social and cultural factor, and the economy factor. Concrete solutions in eradicating corruption needed by Indonesia are redesigning public services, strengthening transparency, supervision and sanctions on government activities related to the economy and human resources, increasing the empowerment of supporting instruments in preventing corruption and to make sure law enforcers are free of corruption. Corruption eradication strategy must be built with the willingness of all parties who want to eradicate corruption itself, by not giving the slightest tolerance in the corrupt acts themselves. In realizing an effort to eradicate corruption itself, it takes a determination in fulfilling the prerequisites in terms of being driven by political ability and will and strong commitment from all parties, transparent and accountable in its implementation, available and balanced resources and capacities.

Keywords: ideology, morality, corruption prevention, juridic

INTRODUCTION

Corruption has been conceptualized and is able to influence decisions that have an orientation to enrich certain individuals (Haryatmoko 2011: 123). Corruption often occurs due to deviations of authority and involvement of more than one person and is carried out in congregation.

Authority is the main cause of an official being entangled in corruption cases. It is very alarming because corrupt behavior is carried out by people on government bureaucracy. As a result, the community suffers the lack of figure who demonstrate good behavior. Through the years, despite the increasing regulations, the implementation has not given strong and firmness in eradicating the corruption crime (Suryani, 2015). This is because there is a reluctance to process violations of corruption crimes caused by the state officials. The subordinates seem to turn a blind eye due to being afraid of the higher ups so that they eventually hold the principle in which as long as the higher ups are happy, they will not do anything. This situation makes the act of corruption rooted continuously in bureaucracy which ultimately gives an example to the community to also practice corruption in the form

of bribery when they do legal administration in order to obtain excellent services from the government (Alpian et al., 2020).

The emergence of such mimic-imitate attitude, omission and normalization culture as well as supported by environmental conditions, suggesting that although the government is well-maintained but there is still the omission of corruption acts happening (Ashinta Sekar Bidari SH & A., 1945). Therefore, the realization of clear and clean governance and good governance cannot be achieved. According to the data from the Corruption Eradication Commission (later will be referred as KPK), commonly, corruption occurred due to bribery (Corruption, 2019). Corruption crimes that the KPK handle were based on too case type (2004-Jun 2019)

Bribery is the most common type of corruption case handled by the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK). 661 cases or 65% of the 1,007 corruption cases handled by the KPK are bribery cases. Based on data from the Anti-Corruption Commission, in 2018, there were 168 cases of bribery and were considered the highest number compared to previous years. Then, in the first six months of 2019, there were 97 cases of bribery or more than half of the same cases found last year (Ramadhana, 2018). (Read Databkoks: Korupsi, Penghambat Utama Investasi di Indonesia).

Even though there have been many corrupt perpetrators caught by the KPK and serving a sentence, but this has not deterred state officials or private parties from harming the country's finances. In fact, the number of criminal acts of corruption has actually increased. In 2018, there were 199 cases of corruption, while during January-June 2019, there were 120 or more cases, which is half of total corruption last year (Read Databoks: from 2004 to 2019, there were 124 Regional Heads who committed corruption). Various actions were taken to reduce the number of corruption acts, both legally and formally, by improving morale and instilling the values of Pancasila. Likewise, at the level of early school to higher education in order to obtain mandatory material on anti-corruption education. As an effort that the government will require Anti-Corruption Education subject into formal curriculum so the subject can be given formally in schools. These various activities show that corrupt behavior is a common enemy because it can threaten the nation's future generations. As an enemy, it is natural that corruption must always be fought and eradicated to its roots (Alfaqi et al., 2017).

Based on the elaboration above, the researchers would like to review of corruption eradication in Indonesia based on the aspect of juridical, morality, and ideology of Pancasila.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researchers used normative legal research method with descriptive analysis. This study applied the philosophical approach to find out efforts carried out by the government to tackle corruption in Indonesia from the juridical and moral aspects of the Indonesian people based on the Pancasila Ideology. (Marzuki, 2010). The concept approach is also used in which the researchers incorporate the views and doctrines that have developed in the jurisprudence to find new idea and principles which are relevant to the investigated issues. Besides that, this study also used statute approach and conceptual approach (Saptomo, 2010).

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Indonesia is a constitutional state as stated in the third amendment of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia Article 1 paragraph 3. As a constitutional state, the interests of the public must be protected. As in paragraph IV of the 1945 amendment: "... ... to form an Indonesian government that protects all Indonesian people ..." All people in Indonesia have rights as the constitution have guaranteed that they can live safely, peacefully, and be spared from any crime. Suryani has emphasized that it is important to enforce law as the only pillar to reduce the number of criminal acts of corruption that fall into the extraordinary crime class. (Syriac, 2015)

Corruption is very much against the rules of juridical forms, the value of national morality, and national ideology. Unconsciously, the impact of corrupt behavior has damaged the economy, the democratic sovereign system, the realization of welfare, and justice.

Even though various policies have been carried out by the government to eradicate corruption, if there is no awareness and assertiveness by the government officials, corruption will not disappear. Reality shows that there are still many corruption cases that are not handled seriously and is convoluted in practice.

According to Lee Kuan Yew in his book, *One Man's View of the World*, which said that Indonesia is actually able to eradicate corruption properly because it is supported by abundant natural resources, has a well-known ideology with virtuous character. Because of the presence of corruption that has entered the stage of violence which lead to the misery of the Indonesian people (Ashinta Sekar Bidari SH & A., 1945).

At present, Indonesia is at its lowest point in terms of economic growth that is considered slow and increasing cases of corruption which has caused a moral decline for the Indonesian people as a whole. Indonesia has been through various problems including increased poverty, unemployment, the low value of the rupiah, and the price of basic necessities is increasingly expensive. Serious problems that must be faced by the state should be solved in various ways. However, the problem of weak implementation of regulations, weak morality, and Pancasila has begun to be marginalized, which lead to problems cannot be solved wisely.

Corruption criminals will be silent if they find out they will remain in power for a long time because of the connections they have in the circle of power. However, it is different from democratic countries, where the type of criminals in democratic countries is far more dangerous than can be imagined that they might be more active and more violent compared to anti-democratic countries. (Ashinta Sekar Bidari SH & A., 1945)

The embodiment of democracy in Indonesia, as a symbol in the state, does not appear in power. Both vertically between the government and the Indonesian people and horizontally between the government and/or fellow citizens. Whereas democracy is a symbol of the identity of the Indonesian people which does not only occur once in five years but is expected to occur every time because democracy has flowed in the veins of the Indonesian people (Robison & Hadiz, 2004).

The concept of constitutional state is demonstrated by the act of rule of law, which means that every person or government as a source of law in which power must be based on applicable law. Equality before the law means that everyone is considered the same without any difference from the various stratifications of life. The explanation of Indonesian Law on State Administrators that is Clean and Free of Corruption, Collusion and Nepotism No. 28 of 1999 is absolute. A clean and well-organized State Government will achieve the National goals easily. This has been stated in the Explanation of the 1945 Constitution which states that the spirit of the Government is important. The practice of criminal acts of corruption, collusion, and nepotism due to crystallized behavior on government officials so that the impact is the corruption not only carried out by the State Administrators, between the State Administrators, but also State Administrators with other parties such as families, business people, and the community. Finally, there is damage to various aspects of community, nation, and state life. If this condition is allowed to drag on without any control, it will threaten the existence of the Republic of Indonesia unity (Patombongi, 2016).

Jeremy Pope in his book, *Confronting Corruption: The Element of the National Integrity System*, explains that corruption has now become a global problem because it does not only occur in Indonesia. Corruption practices will not be possible if only one person does it, it can be carried out when two or more people or even group of individuals share mutual benefits. Without understanding that behind the fun and joy of using the money which actually come from the tax payers, such lowly act makes people suffer. Since it is very clear that corruption triggers gaps in social life in which it promotes the principle of the rich get richer and the poor get poorer.

Countries with corruption practices are certainly having an authoritarian configuration as in the case of the concept of totalitarian government, a dictator who places power in the hands of a few people (Brady et al., 2007).

Although it is known that the configuration of democracy in legal politics by Mahfud MD who stated that democratic power places people and power in a balanced way, gives space to the House of Representatives, gives the executive role and also gives freedom to the press or journalists without any pressure from power (MD, 2009). But in practice, most of all countries have claimed the country takes place in a democracy, but practically is viler than authoritarian rule.

Since corruption is global issue, it is necessary to eradicate it globally. Therefore, corruption is labelled as an extraordinary crime. The Integrated of the Criminal Justice System, If we look at the format of Indonesian Law on the Criminal Procedure Code No. 8 of 1981, it will appear that the integrated system in which the legislators formulate the stage and authority in which the investigation is carried out by the police and certain Civil Servants are given authority by the constitution, then the prosecution stage is carried out by the prosecutor and the stage of hearing is done by the District Court Judge, the High Court and the Supreme Court as well as the implementation of the decision that has permanent legal force (*inkracht van gewijsde*) by the prosecutor and the Penitentiary.

The Public Prosecutor who is in charge of the case then makes an alternative indictment against the defendant. An alternative indictment applied by the Public Prosecutor against the defendant, based on Article 2 paragraph (1) juncto Article 18 of Indonesian Law No. 20 of 2001 on Amendments to Indonesian Law No. 31 of 1999 on Eradication of Corruption Crimes (Corruption Act) juncto Article 64 paragraph (1) of the Indonesian Criminal Code or Article 10 Letter 'a' juncto Article 18 of the Anti-Corruption Act juncto Article 64 paragraph (1) of the Criminal Code. As for the description of articles of

Indonesian Law on Eradication of Corruption Crimes (Corruption Law) No. 31 of 1999 can be explained as follows:

Article 2 paragraph (1) of the Indonesian Anti-Corruption Law states that:

Any person who unlawfully commits acts of enriching oneself or another person or a corporation that can be detrimental to the State finances or the State's economy is punished with life imprisonment or imprisonment for a minimum of 4 (four) years and a maximum of 20 (twenty) years and a minimum fine of Rp. 200,000,000, - (two hundred million rupiah) and a maximum of Rp. 1,000,000,000, - (one hundred billion rupiah).

Article 3 of the Indonesian Anti-Corruption Law states that:

Any person who has the purpose of benefiting himself or another person or a corporation, abuses its existing authority, opportunity or means because of a position or function that can harm the State finances or the State's economy, is punished with life imprisonment or imprisonment for a minimum of 1 (one) year and a maximum of 20 (twenty) years and a fine of at least Rp. 50,000,000, - (fifty million rupiah) and a maximum of Rp. 1,000,000,000, - (one hundred billion rupiah).

Article 10 letter A of the Indonesian Anti-Corruption Law states that:

The perpetrator gets imprisonment with a minimum of 2 (two) years and a maximum imprisonment of 7 (seven) years and a minimum fine of Rp. 100,000,000, - (one hundred million rupiah) and a maximum of Rp. 350,000,000, - (three hundred and fifty million rupiah), the civil servant or individual other than civil servant who is given the task of carrying out a public position continuously or temporarily, who intentionally:

a. Embezzle, destroy, damaging, or defect the goods, certificate, letter or lists that are used as evidence to the official, who is controlled by his position. Article 18 of the Indonesian Anti-Corruption Law states that:

1) In addition to the additional crimes referred to in the Criminal Code Act, as additional Crimes are:

- a. Confiscation of tangible or intangible immovable property or immovable property used for or obtained from a criminal act of corruption, including a convict-owned company where a criminal act of corruption is committed, as well as from items that replace the stated items.
- b. Payment of replacement money in the amount of - as much as the property obtained from criminal acts of corruption.
- c. Closure of all or part of the company for a maximum period of 1 (one) year.
- d. Revocation of all or part of certain rights or the elimination of all or part of certain benefits, which have been or can be given by the government to the convicted person.

2) If the convicted person does not pay substitute money as referred to in paragraph (1) letter b no later than 1 (one) month after the court's decision has obtained permanent legal force, then his property can be confiscated by the prosecutor and auctioned off to cover the replacement money.

3) In case the convict does not have sufficient assets to pay the replacement money as referred to in paragraph (1) letter b, the convict shall be imprisoned for a period not exceeding the maximum threat of the principal in accordance with the provisions in this constitution and the duration of the imprisonment has been determined in the court's decision. Furthermore, article 64 paragraph (1) of the Criminal Code states that "If between several acts, though each is a crime or an offense, related in such a way that it must be seen as an act of corruption, then only one criminal rule, if different, what is applied is the one contains the most serious basic criminal threats. "The judge, based on the indictment, saw several articles (alternative indictments) that were indicted against the defendant. The judge will act to decide a crime by referring to the form and nature of the indictment. The judge is also authorized to choose and decide which articles they think are related to criminal acts committed by the defendant. In the verdict, it was discovered that the judge found the defendant guilty of violating Article 3 of Indonesian Law on Eradication of Corruption No. 31 of 1999 (Pasaribu et al., 2008).

Morality

Almost every day we watch on television or read in the mass media that corruption still happens wherever and whenever. Every corruptor is arrested, even though it is considered as an achievement of law enforcement, but in terms of culture, this is a tragic side of a corrupt mentality that is unstoppable. In this context, corruption is a tragedy of cultural morality that is currently in distressed.

There is a condition in the nature of Indonesian culture that encourages people to commit acts of corruption. Likewise, there are cultural constraints as to why corruption remains so massive, that eradication of corruption is always never completely carried out.

Such reality shows that corruption is not just a legal problem, but also a matter of culture. This research is in many ways a literature research that seeks to uncover cultural barriers in eradicating corruption in Indonesia, although the researchers do not ignore the empirical reality in the form of public perception and construction related to the problem of corruption in Indonesia which is carried out using a phenomenological approach. This approach is needed in order to reveal the real condition of the community related to the phenomenon of corruption that has been comprehend and perceived by the public (Listiyono Santoso, Dewi Meyriswati, 2014).

Corruption is said to be a destructive thing that can make a nation corrupted. Corruption has been considered as a normal thing, with the pretext that according to the procedure, the corruptor no longer has shame and fear.

Corruption is a violation of social rights and economic rights of the community. So that corruption is classified as extraordinary crimes. Corruption eradication must be carried out comprehensively and together with law enforcement, community institutions, and all individual members of the community.

Government action to enforce the law is the supremacism of constitution and the concept of constitutional state. Law enforcement in full compliance with the principle that stands where the law is absolute. If the commitment on law enforcement has become a culture, then arbitrariness is no longer found. The atmosphere of democracy in accordance with the characteristics of the Indonesian nation can be realized in the forms of people's sovereignty and legal sovereignty (Patombongi, 2016).

Corruption is part of a violation of human rights. Corruption has damaging effect and impact on people's welfare. It can even kill human hence it is an extraordinary crime. In general, what was corrupted was state money by weakening an authority or position. To perpetuate a position, a bribe method can be used. In this case, the highest corrupt practices in Indonesia were done through bribery.

Resolving a corruption case which is an extraordinary crime is certainly not easy. Therefore, in Indonesia, an independent institution was formed which was equipped with regulatory instruments to be able to reach corruption cases. An independent institution is called the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK).

Corruption in the Study of Law and Human Rights (Pricilia Ryana, Aisy Idzati 181) Indonesia is currently struggling to organize itself to overcome corruption by amending and revising laws and regulations in order to resolve highly problematic issues such as Corruption. Starting by making changes to Military Law No. PRT/PM/06/1975 by the Central War Rule Regulation of the Indonesian Army No. PRT/PEPERPU/03/1958, amended by Indonesian Law No. 24/Prp/1960, amended by Indonesian Law No. 3 of 1971, then in the era of President Megawati Sukarnoputri's reign, Indonesian Law No. 3 of 1971 was amended by Indonesian Law on Eradication of Corruption No. 31 of 1999, and as a refinement of the law above, it is complemented by Indonesian Law No. 20 of 2001. In the Corruption Law No. 31 of 1999 there were 4 (four) fundamental reforms (M. Yahya Harahap, 2002: 68-69), such as:

1. Corruption perpetrators must be tried and convicted;
2. Laws in Indonesia adhere to a system of pure reverse proof; that the defendant before a court hearing is required to prove that his assets were not the result of corruption. If the defendant is able to show evidence that can convince the judge, the defendant can be acquitted. Likewise, if the defendant is unable to show evidence, then the defendant can be sentenced to a criminal sentence. Thus, the principle of the law must include physical evidence and refute statements that cannot be proven. Furthermore, the sentences to the defendants can be given in various ways according to the quality or amount of the embezzled money. The shortest period is 1 (one) year to 3 (three) years, and the longest is between 10 years or 15 years or according to the Criminal Code that has been adopted in the criminal justice process approximately 20 years ago;
3. Bribes perpetrator gets to pay fine as much as Rp. 10,000,000, - unless proven. Bribery is also called formal offense;
4. Confiscation of the assets of the defendant can be carried out both before and after the decision of the court and not limited by time.

Furthermore, according to Arief, what must be considered is the legal culture. If the legal culture of the people and law enforcers is weak then it is impossible for corruption to be eradicated (Arief, 2003: 87). State management always refers to the principles of clean government and good governance. Thus, it can suppress the increasing number of corruptions which is accompanied by a legal culture. Because the nature of the regulations is abstract and will not have power if the subject is weak to the

law. Therefore, the spirit of the state officials is very much needed which certainly can provide positive energy to all people.

The chaos that often arises in the community is caused by a community control system that is not functioning or does not exist at all. Chaos can be triggered by acts of corruption committed by the community. For example, the practice of local elections and procurement of subsidies from the government to the community. Distribution of groceries, subsidies in the form of money or goods is also corrupted by the community. As a result, the community's situation became chaotic with the non-distribution of all subsidies. Not even on target which cause gaps in the community. This is a form of moral deviation as a massive impact of corruption.

According to Theobald, due to internal corruption: it raises the attitude of greed, ignorance, and do not care about others. Likewise, Cahndar Muzaffar stated that the cause of internal corruption is to underestimate other people, and is very individualistic (Setiadi, 2018).

The massive effects of corruption damage the mentality of the next generation; the disappearance of adult role models who should give good example that can be replicated by current generations; damage the mindset of generations; the next generation considers that all problems can only be solved by bribing. As a result of the life of the future nation's successors will be on the verge of darkness.

The legal politics of a country with massive practices of corruption impacts on an authoritarian government system. It is strange if this condition occurs in a democratic, but authoritarian Indonesian system. In the end, the community is tired of the losing their trust towards the government and will not obey the rules on daily basis which actually should be practice accordingly.

Corruption practice is the reason why bureaucracy is unstable and over budget administration. We also often found a very bad form of service; the working hours are not taken seriously therefore it fails to meet the public's expectation who need a good public service. In fact, it often seems that when dealing with government bureaucratic administration, there is a difference in services between those who have connection with the officer than people who does not (Setiadi, 2018).

As a result, a public mindset is formed that if it has affairs that deal with the government bureaucratic administration, they must prepare a sum of money to facilitate administrative matters. If so, it means that the practice of corruption in the form of bribery has been entrenched in the community.

Efforts to eradicate corruption have been initiated since 1950 but it turns out that until now it has not produced significant results. This condition shows that the massive practice of corruption is rooted and entrenched. It is the will of an elite party to justify it enriching itself by ignoring legal principles (Nature, 2017).

The nature of a law is to be a relation in a power so that there is no lower or higher power. But in fact, it is very feasible if the law used as a guide in power. Then, through power, it can force people to obey, and vice versa, power must really obey the law (Handoyo, 2003: 272). The constitution that forms a country exists to limit the power so that it is not arbitrary.

Corruption is an extraordinary crime because it can threaten the sustainability of the nation. Besides, it was also threatening the stability and security of the country as well as the entire community, obstruct social and economic development of society, politics, and may even undermine democratic values, morality and add sovereign debt.

The presence of Indonesian Law on the Corruption Eradication Commission No. 30 of 2002 gives the task to the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) to conduct an investigation and prosecution of corruption. The task of the KPK is to coordinate with authorized institutions to eradicate corruption, supervise agencies that are authorized to eradicate corruption, take preventive measures against corruption, and monitor the implementation of state government.

If someone is announced as suspect by KPK, then starting from the announcement date, the special procedures within the framework of the examination of suspect regulated in other law is not valid under Article 46 of Indonesian Law on the Commission eradication Corruption Crime No. 30 of 2002 (Ryana & Idzati, 2018).

Pancasila Ideology

The act of bribing to extortion for the sake of personal and group interests in corruption, collusion and nepotism has a profound impact on daily life, especially the first principle of Pancasila, namely *Belief in the Almighty God*. Corruption, collusion and nepotism are clearly a form of betrayal to God who has created humans as caliphs whose creation purpose is to spread goodness.

But what happened was actually damaging their personality due to a very chronic deviant act of corruption which meant that inside them have no longer had the virtue values that God had entrusted to them. Corruption clearly undermines the second principle which is A just and civilized humanity. The

human side of the corruptors is questioned in seeing the losses incurred such as poverty and unemployment which are increasingly rampant due to acts of corruption, collusion and nepotism that seem to have ingrained in the mentality of the corruptors.

The third principle of Pancasila, the Unity of Indonesia, has clearly stated that corruption, collusion, and nepotism are very detrimental and destroys the unity and integrity of the Indonesian state because of the many crimes inflicted by corruption that continue without the strong law enforcement of the Indonesian people. In the fourth principle of Pancasila, *Citizens, led by collective wisdom in representation*, in fact corruption is not in accordance with the noble culture of the Indonesian people who uphold the values of deliberative and consensus democracy where in the principle of deliberation, the Indonesian nation is able to solve all the problems of the nation without doing corruption practice, collusion and nepotism are known to greatly destroy the values of democracy itself.

The fifth principle of Pancasila, *Social equity for all the peoples of Indonesia*, corruption, collusion and nepotism are proven to clearly tarnish the sense of justice of Indonesian people with very destructive practices among the elite by making maximum profits without thinking of the overall interests of the Indonesian nation and state.

With Pancasila principles that are related to the behavior of corruption, collusion and nepotism, Indonesian people are expected to avoid all forms of corruption without exception, because Indonesia is a country that upholds the law as the main guideline in carrying out the life of the nation and state, in Article 1 Paragraph (3) 1945 Constitution which states that "Indonesia is a constitutional state". A rule of law is a country that is based on laws and regulations; a country that can take care of the people well, able to create prosperity and eliminate inequalities in people's lives. On the other hand, the people must obey the applicable regulations and are not allowed to violate the rule of law.

Causes of Corruption in Indonesia

According to Arifianto (2004) that there are three theories as the key for dealing with corruption in Indonesia, they are described as follows:

First, the *mainstream economic theory* explains that the state often acts as a monopoly on the country's economic activities.

Second, the *patrimonialism theory*; this theory argues that corruption can act as a way to increase political integration between ethnic groups, parties and factions in government.

Third, *Kleptocratic state theory*; this theory states that endemic corruption is in a regime that is controlled by a state leader who has a goal through their position only to enrich themselves.

Harold D. Laswell in *Who Gets What, When, how* said that: "Politics is a matter of who gets what, when, and how". Based on this opinion, the way someone gets public power in certain ways, for example, when a person obtains an official position in the government by practicing money politics, and then when they are carrying out their job, they have the potential to commit unlawful acts of corruption although corruption is an unlawful act because it distorts public power for certain interests (I Ketut Patra, 2018).

Factors that cause corruption:

- a. Internal factors; that is a factor within the individual, for example the existence of human greed; weak morality when it comes to temptation; consumptive lifestyle and laziness or the urge to get easy money through the position one holds.
- b. External factors; factors from outside oneself such as: aspects of individual behavior; organizational aspects; aspects of society where individuals and organizations are located; Lack of example and leadership of the nation's elites; low salaries of civil servants or employees; weak commitment and consistency in law enforcement and legislation; low integrity and professionalism; internal oversight mechanisms in all banking, financial and bureaucratic institutions are not yet established; working environment conditions, job duties, and the community environment; lack of faith, honesty, shame, morals and ethics.

Corruption can be manifested in the act of reducing the quality of government services, infrastructure and adding pressure on the government budget, the cost of goods and services, which leads to the realization and the difficulty of the people to be able to live in prosperous demands for the use of the state budget and income by the public ignored by the government. (I Ketut Patra, 2018).

Barriers to Eradicating Corruption

- a. Structural Barriers, the lack of seriousness of law enforcement officials to deal thoroughly with corruption cases so that corruption cases often occur that are not completed for years. The lack of seriousness of the government can be caused by the existence of sectorial and institutional egoism which leads to the submission of as much funds for the sector and its institutions without regard to the overall national needs and seeks to cover up the deviations in the relevant sectors and

agencies; the supervision function ineffectively; weak coordination between the supervisory officers and law enforcement officers; and weak internal control system that has a positive correlation with various irregularities and inefficiencies in the management of state assets and the low quality of public services.

- b. Cultural Barriers, such as a stereotype attitude in resolving corruption cases so that the handling cannot be completed. Stereotype means the formation of wrong understanding, immediately applying legal sanctions to people whom they recognized or older than them. The emergence of practices of interfering with the affairs of existing Institutions so that the rules are weakened by an understanding of mutual forgiveness.
- c. Instrumental barriers, i.e. a lack of infrastructure support in the form of legislation which makes the handling of corruption cases cannot be conducted optimally. This can happen if the regulations do not support each other or even are not harmonious.
- d. Management obstacles, the willingness to apply the principle of good governance in government bureaucracy hence it is not transparent, not accountable, unprofessional and not responsible and does not involve public participation.

The examples that occur according to (Suryani, 2015) are:

- a. Taking state money secretly,
- b. Force people to act outside their authority,
- c. Violating the law,
- d. Taking state assets,
- e. Accept bribes,
- f. Covering a fraud up committed by officials by lying.

According to Dreher, Kostogiannis and McCorriston (2004) there are four factors that cause corruption, such as:

First, political, judicial and historical factors.

Second, social and cultural factors are essentially related to moral attitudes. People who have commendable moral qualities tend to distance themselves from acts of corruption. They tend to make decisions and implement programs in a variety of activities and tend to avoid acts that harm others and vice versa. Social and cultural factors play a special role in identifying the level of corruption of a country, according to La Porta (1999), Treisman (2000) and Alesina (2003). Religion and social systems have an influence in suppressing corruption.

Third, economic factors, such as economic openness (Dreher, 2006; Treisman, 2000), public sector in the economy (Tanzi, 1998; Treisman, 2000), the level of remuneration in the public sector (Rijckeghem and Weder, 1997), have direct impact on the level of corruption in a country. Furthermore, Aguilera and Vadera (2008) distinguish the typology of corruption based on the complexity and practice of corruption throughout the world.

According to Henderson and Kuncoro (2012), the flow of political parties in Indonesia suggests that political parties is kind of a dominant factor that affect the level of corruption in a period and region in Indonesia, such as parties based on religion, in this case Islam is less corrupt than non-religious based parties' ones. The fraud and corruption mode are carried out by bribing politicians and law enforcers and bureaucratic officials in getting services (I Ketut Patra, 2018).

The emergence of corruption and human rights crimes cannot be separated from uncontrolled power or abuse of power. In this case, according to Muladi, given that it is often said that the source or opportunity of corruption is the granting of a monopoly of power to a person or institution accompanied by the authority to conduct extensive discretion (taxation, customs, law enforcement, immigration), there must be strict supervision and control of the monopolistic and discretionary authority. The need for control of power in order to be able to respond to corrupt practices and human rights crimes are implemented in several forms, such as a strong civil society, proportional press, universities with integrity, strong NGOs, and responsive social and religious organizations. The New Order regime cannot be separated from its links with political corruption and human rights violations, because the president and his officials had, in some cases, been indicated, suspected, charged and convicted. In relation to the Human Rights Court in Indonesia, Muladi argued, systemically, Indonesia had held an East Timor Human Rights Court and another Human Rights Court (Tanjung Priok), which occurred in the period before the Indonesian Law No. 26 of 2000 was promulgated. The steps are carried out systemically because the Human Rights Court must adjudicate "extraordinary crime" so it is not permitted to use the formulation of "ordinary crimes" that are regulated in national law (KUHP etc.); for that, with the method of "partial harmonization," in Indonesian Law No. 26 of 2000 adopted the formulation of criminal acts, especially those related to "genocide" and "crimes against humanity" and several other provisions taken from the Rome Statute in 1998. This was done because Indonesia had

not ratified the statute. Political corruption and related human rights violations were also carried out by state leaders such as Suharto, Marcos, Reza Pahlavi, Pinochet, and others.

Hahn Been Lee (in Susilo Zauhar, 1996) categorizes reforms into:

- a. Order reform, the reformation of procedures of traditional and modern societies who are very fond of order, especially in transitional (prismatic) societies that are carrying out massive reforms. In this situation, people like to reminisce about the old order. To overcome these problems, reform needs to be directed at creating procedures and establishing routines. Reform must be oriented towards structuring procedures and controls to block reform agents so that reforms do not cause chaos.
- b. Reform of the Method, reformation of the order improvement technique is a product of chaos, while the impetus for perfecting the method arises because of the eradication of corruption in Indonesia emerged because of the stimulant from the community. If the public increasingly supports the existence of technical administrators rather than status, administrators must be fanatical about the method. Public administrators in society who have advanced technologically are required to be more fanatical about the development of techniques and methods.
- c. Performance Reform, a program of performance improvement that is more nuanced objectives in the substance of the program rather than perfecting order and perfecting administrative technical methods. The main focus is the shift from form to substance, from efficiency and economics to work effectiveness, from bureaucratic skills to public welfare. Not only aims at law and order or procedural, or the search for new methods and techniques, but it also focuses on the output (Ryana & Idzati, 2018).

Related to this, at least there is an extraordinary instrument that tends to get more attention in the legislation policy to eradicate corruption as adopted and formulated in Indonesian Law No. 31 of 1999 as amended by Indonesian Law No. 20 of 2001. One of the instruments is the application of the reverse onus clause system (*omkering van de bewijslast*). This instrument deviates from the general principles of criminal law as formulated in the Criminal Code (KUHP). In the Criminal Procedure Code the principle is that the defendant is not burdened with the obligation of proof because the evidence in a criminal case is the burden of the public prosecutor in accordance with the adage "*Actory incumbit onus probandi*" which means whoever is accused then he is the one who must prove the indictment. The application of the reverse onus system is also considered to be in contact with the presumption of innocence and the principle of not self-blame (non-self-incrimination)."

The emergence of instruments that have been formulated in Indonesian Law No. 31 of 1999 as amended by Indonesian Law No. 20 of 2001 is very necessary considering the eradication and prevention of corruption by the government so far has not shown the direction of change and the results as is expected. This condition raises strong pressure from the public who want the realization of various concrete steps by the government and other high state institutions in eradicating and preventing corruption.

The implementation of this system is expected to be able to eliminate the level of proof of difficulties encountered so far in eradicating criminal acts of corruption which tend to be done very neatly and thoroughly. In addition, the application of this reversal onus is a means and a legal breakthrough in the context of criminal law reformation that can be taken by the government to eradicate corruption that has taken root in Indonesia. The application of this system in the experience of several countries, such as Malaysia, Singapore and Hong Kong have proven quite effective in reducing corruption (Syahroni et al., 2019).

Corruption is a very crucial problem in the world, one example in Brazil, the corruption case in Petrobras, a national oil company owned by the Brazilian state that has corruption cases that dragged many officials in the country. In the case that ensnared these officials and entrepreneurs, it should be a warning to all of us that corruption affects all countries in the world and has been rooted in every level of society indiscriminately (Lima-de-Oliveira, 2019).

Corruption in Indonesia has brought political-economic-social disharmony. It could even be a new culture in this beloved country, graphs of growth in the number of poor people continue to rise because of increasingly rampant corruption. In the life of democracy in Indonesia, corrupt practices are more easily found in various fields of life. First, because of the weakening of social values, personal interests are the first choice compared to the public interest, and the ownership of objects individually becomes the personal ethic that underlies the social behavior of most people. Secondly, there is no transparency and accountability for public integrity systems. Public service bureaus are actually used by public officials to pursue personal political ambitions, solely for the sake of promotion. While the quality and quantity of public services is increasingly being ignored, it is not the main priority and orientation and

these two reasons have emerged in Indonesia, public services have never been maximized because corruption and democratic practices, they actually facilitate the corruption act instead.

The cause of corruption includes two factors, internal factors and external factors. Internal factors are a cause of corruption that comes from individual itself while external factors are factors that cause corruption due to external causes. Internal factors consist of moral aspects, such as lack of faith, honesty, shame, attitude or behavior aspects such as consumptive lifestyle. External factors from economic aspects such as insufficient income, political aspects such as political interests, gaining and maintaining power, management & organization aspects, lack of accountability and transparency, legal aspects, are seen in the poor form of legislation and weak law enforcement and social aspects, namely an environment that encourages the fertility of corruption itself.

In fact, there are many ways to stop corruption significantly, such as strengthening anti-corruption education in schools, tight supervision of financial transactions, mental revolutions in Indonesian society and so on. However, very little effort has been made by various parties in eradicating this practice of corruption because it is still rooted in the culture of feudalism in our society that has led to corruption that is increasingly rampant everywhere.

One of the countermeasures that is considered effective is a mental revolution carried out for the Indonesian people in a total and consistent manner, but there are still many organs of society that do not understand and do not aware of what and how to interpret mental revolution which is expected to change the order of the negative behavior of Indonesian people that is still far from the expectations of all parties who hope negative behavior such as corruption can disappear from Indonesia. The Indonesian people are still struggling with this problem because the mentality that has not changed at all either from the Indonesian nation or from outside influences such as changes caused by increasingly globalization which causes changes in the lives of Indonesian people who are increasingly consumptive which results in criminal acts of corruption in almost all levels of Indonesian society as a whole.

Corruption does not only affect one aspect of life. Corruption has a widespread domino effect on the existence of nation and state. Nowadays, corruption is no longer perceived as something that only harms the country's finances and/or economy, but should be seen as something that violates social rights and economic rights of the community as part of human rights. Therefore, there are sufficient rational reasons to categorize corruption as an extraordinary crime. So, in an effort to eradicate it is no longer carried out normally, but requires extraordinary ways (extraordinary enforcement).

In the perspective of criminal law, corruption is classified as a very dangerous form of crime. The financial losses of the state and the country's economy are the real consequences which are the basis of the justification of the criminalization of various forms of corrupt behavior in criminal law policies. Various ways have been done to eradicate this crime, but it turns out that corruption still exists, grows and develops in tune with developments society, so that it becomes increasingly difficult to eradicate.

Widespread corruption practices in a country will worsen the nation's economic conditions, for example, the price of goods becomes expensive with poor quality, people's access to education and health becomes difficult, the security of a country is threatened, environmental damage, and a bad image of government in the international eye so that it destabilizes joints of the trust of foreign capital owners, a prolonged economic crisis, and the country is increasingly mired in poverty.

Pancasila must also become the strongest fortress in the fight against corruption in this country by strengthening the implementation of Pancasila values to all levels of society, especially the younger generation who are currently undergoing their education in every school and university in the country. However, the application of the principles of Pancasila and the strengthening of the character of Pancasila which lead to anti-corruption education must be aligned with real behavior and its application directly on the field. Without direct application, what has been echoed by all parties in upholding the values of Pancasila coupled with anti-corruption education becomes futile. Indonesia's Human Development Index must also be considered in looking at the benchmarks of law enforcement in Indonesia, especially in this case, law enforcement against corruption because the fight against corruption must also reaffirm the strength and resilience of Indonesian people in fighting corruption by preparing quality resources Indonesian people who are prepared better in the fight against corruption itself.

Previously, the notion of corruption, the factors that cause corruption and the impact of corruption have been explained. Some say that the most appropriate effort to eradicate corruption is to punish the perpetrators. Thus, in the field of law, especially criminal law will be considered as the most appropriate answer to eradicate corruption. It is a reality that we already have various legal instruments to eradicate corruption, the laws and regulations in force in Indonesia which regulate corruption. We have institutions and law enforcement agencies that are dedicated to carry out the corruption law, police, prosecutors and courts. We even have an independent institution called the Corruption Eradication Commission

(KPK), all of which were formed, one of which was to eradicate corruption. But what actually happens is that corruption continues to flourish and develop rapidly.

Legislation policies, especially in the field of criminal law, have experienced extraordinary dynamics as a response and manifestation of turmoil towards the problem of corruption that has plagued the Indonesian people. There is hardly a single criminal offense that receives an extraordinary response and attention from legislative policies other than criminal acts of corruption. Various efforts have been made in an effort to eradicate criminal acts of corruption, both those that are preventive and repressive (prosecution). In fact, the regulation on corruption has changed several times. (Syahroni et al., 2019)

In the latest data, the Corruption Eradication Commission said that it had carried out 87 arrest operations (OTT) with 327 initial suspects during 2015-2019. The operation was mostly carried out in 2018, as many as 30 cases with 121 suspects. In addition to OTT, the KPK has conducted 498 investigations, 539 inquisitions, 433 prosecutions, 286 permanent legal decisions, and 383 executions in the last four years. Anti-Corruption Behavior Index (IPAK) of Indonesian people in 2019 is 3.7 from a scale of 0-5. The rate is higher than the 2018 IPAK which was 3.66. The higher the index (close to 5), the higher the anticorruption behavior in the community is.

Although the IPAK improved in general, one of the dimensions of the IPAK recorded a decline. The dimension of anti-corruption perception in 2019 is at the level of 3.8 or lower than the previous year which was 3.86. The decline in the dimensions of the perception of anti-corruption is influenced by several factors, such as; first, the community considers it reasonable to give money or goods to other community leaders when a family is celebrating. As a result, the perception dimension decreased from 41.36 in 2018 to 40.93 in 2019.

Second, the community considers it normal for parents to invite their children in the election campaign to get more money so that the score drops from 12.61 in 2018 to 12.88 in 2019. The dimensions of the experience of anti-corruption improve with an index of 3.65 in 2019 from 3, 57 in 2018.

Indonesia's corruption perception index in 2019 is 40 points. This figure is higher by 2 points compared to the previous year which was 38. Despite the increase, *Transparency International* noted that the independence and effectiveness of the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK) was weakened by the Indonesian government.

Enforcement sector is one of the important instruments for eradicating corruption, because law enforcement is believed to have a *detern effect* for perpetrators. Based on that, the KPK's task is specifically mentioned in Article 6 letter e of Indonesian Law on the Corruption Eradication Commission No. 19 of 2019 to investigate, investigate and prosecute corruption. At the very least, the performance of KPK's actions is a sector that receives direct attention from the public.

If we look at the action taken by the KPK, it almost always increases every year. The peak will be in 2018, where the KPK raised 199 cases to the level of inquisition. This figure exceeds the previous period, for example in 2017, were 121 cases and in 2016, were 99 cases. In fact, specifically for arrest operation, in 2018 the KPK made history by carrying out the largest number of arrest operations (OTT), 28 times and determining 108 suspects (Ramadhana, 2019).

The attention of various groups of society and even ordinary people about corruption shows that, in fact, every individual in the community individually has the will to be better by contributing to this problem. In addition, concerns from various sections of the community also show that the problem of corruption actually has a destructive social impact. In other words, the problem of corruption is a social problem because it involves the lives of many people (social society) in Indonesia (Tamawiyw-Karundeng, 2015).

Talking about the social aspect, Perlas (2001) warns that social life always consists of three critical subsystems (three sub-systems), politics, economy, and culture. These three sub-systems are also called 'three sociological pillars'. The interaction of these three pillars determines what kind of social life we live in Indonesia. According to Perlas, we will live in healthy social conditions if these three pillars support each other and develop their respective abilities to realize that each pillar can have a strong influence on the other two.

In other words, Perlas also said that the dominance of one or more pillars so that overriding or even conquering one or two others in social life leads to unhealthy social life. This conception of social formation is an effort for the distribution of power that values culture as well as a foundation that stands parallel to politics and economics. According to Perlas, these three pillars are usually represented by three key institutions that influence social life.

Perlas points out several different functions of the three pillars, one of which is about 'relationship bases'. The basis of government relations is the rules / laws (rules). Basic business relationship is the

transactions. Whereas the basis of civil society organization relations is values. In relation to corruption, if we look at the approaches offered to solve the problem of corruption in Indonesia, then we can say that social life in Indonesia is not fully healthy yet. The approaches offered up to now are still one-sided because it is not uncommon to set aside the third pillar that is a culture which also talks a lot about human values and even spirituality (I Ketut Patra, 2018).

This is a contrast to the agenda of President Joko Widodo (Jokowi), which is encouraging foreign investment and improving the economy. Due to the problem of corruption is making investors worry and can slow down economic progress. The 2019 corruption perception index survey involved 180 countries. A score of 0 means that the country is very corrupt, while a score of 100 indicates the country is clean from corruption.

In the social and state life structure, Indonesia cannot be separated from Muhammadiyah and Nadlatul Ulama and vice versa. In the perspective of the legal eradication and corruption prevention fronted by the Corruption Eradication Commission (KPK). Even the moral movement to eradicate corruption has also begun in 2003 fronted by NU and Muhammadiyah in the Moment of Understanding (MoU) about the national moral movement to eradicate Corruption (Nasution, 1999).

So far, there has been an assumption that the difficulty in eradicating corruption in Indonesia is a result of an understanding that corruption is the nation's culture. This understanding needs to be clarified by showing that the culture of the Indonesian people is anti-corruption. Indonesia is a country that is pluralistic in terms of ethnicity, culture, language, beliefs and religion. This diversity results in the diversity (pluralism) of law as an unavoidable fact.

The cultural transformation of the archipelago into a legal development format, specifically the eradication of corruption, originates from 2 (two) important elements: first, taken from religious values; and second, derived from customary values. The culture of the archipelago that originates from religious values, among others, can be seen from the view of Islam which states that: "Corruption to enrich oneself from state assets is an act of zhalim (persecution), because state wealth is property, collected from the community including the poor, they have obtained by with great effort. In fact, these actions have a very broad impact and have an impact on adding to the quantity of new poor people" (Muhlizi, 2014).

In the modern era, everything has changed, a very noble word is replaced by something that smells of material, namely the statement of financial position, income statement, statement of changes in capital and cash flow statement. This is the beginning of the problem, how much accounting fraud in the world such as Enron, Xerox, Kanebo, and others. The latest in Indonesia is how a senior BPK auditor was arrested by the KPK for committing fraud.

Actually, looking at the data above, all parties can conclude that efforts to tackle corruption are still far below the expectations of all parties who still care about law enforcement against corruption in Indonesia. Moreover, there is the issue of weakening the KPK and the Government that tends to open investment taps by reducing the pressure of "terror" law enforcement against corruption from the KPK and the anti-corruption community rather than supporting it with moral responsibility and actions that prevent it all. Therefore, people who are aware of the threat of corruption must be able to convince all parties, including the government, to pay more attention to the latent dangers of corruption and to intensify efforts to tackle corruption on all fronts of Indonesian society (I Ketut Patra, 2018).

Corruption Prevention Solutions

To overcome these obstacles, the following steps have been and are being implemented:

- a. Redesigning public services, especially in areas directly related to daily service activities to the community. The aim is to make it easier for the wider community to obtain professional, good quality, timely services and without being charged extra fees. Priority steps are aimed at: (a) Improving the Public Service System; (b) Improving the Performance of Public Service Officers; (c) Improving the Performance of Public Service Institutions; and (d) Increased Supervision of Public Services.
- b. Strengthen transparency, supervision and sanctions on government activities related to the economy and human resources. The aim is to increase the accountability of the Government in managing state and human resources as well as providing access to information and various things that further provide opportunities for the wider community to participate in the economic field. Priority steps are aimed at: (a) Improving the State Financial Management System; (b) Improving the Government Procurement System; and (c) Improving the State Officials HR Management System.
- c. Increasing the empowerment of supporting tools in preventing corruption. The aim is to uphold the principle of "rule of law," strengthening the legal culture and empowering the community in the

process of eradicating corruption. Priority steps are aimed at: (a) Raising Awareness and Community Participation; and (b) Completion of Supporting Legal Materials.

- d. It seems that entering a correctional facility (prison) for corruptors is not a deterrent or the most effective way to eradicate corruption. Moreover, in prisons, the practice actually becomes a place that is no different from places outside the prison where the origin of the corrupt prisoners can pay a sum of money to get services and facilities that are not different from services and facilities outside the correctional facility. Therefore, the term penitentiary appears with luxurious facilities and services. Looking at this condition, it is necessary to think of other ways so that people feel embarrassed and rethink about doing corruption. The way to do this is the provision to announce a decision that has obtained permanent legal force over a corruption case through the mass media. This provision not only provides information to the public but also acts as a moral sanction for perpetrators of criminal acts of corruption. In addition, sanctions should be added to the revocation of rights to defendants in corruption cases. This is very important to provide learning that the bearer of public office is a moral and high integrity person. Law enforcement in the context of combating corruption must be carried out in an integrated manner with one goal: to eradicate corruption. Law enforcement human resources must come from chosen people and have high integrity. It is time to end the occurrence of sectorial egos or institutional egos among law enforcement agencies. The state also needs to think about how to make the level of welfare for law enforcers good, not lacking anything and becoming clean law enforcers (Setiadi, 2018).

Corruption Eradication Strategy must be built with the willingness of all parties who want to eradicate the corruption itself by not giving the slightest tolerance in the corrupt acts themselves. In realizing the effort to eradicate corruption, it takes a determination in fulfilling the prerequisites in the following terms:

- a. Driven by political ability and will and strong commitment from all parties
- b. Transparent and accountable in its implementation
- c. Existing resources and capacities
- d. Balanced and measured

CONCLUSION

Some efforts to prevent corruption through formal juridical aspects: the compliance of legal institutions in the implementation of corruption eradication in Indonesia. In an effort to strengthen the implementation of law enforcement.

Moral aspect: character building among the young generation of the Indonesian people. The younger generation as agents of change who can control the wheels of government in accordance with the conscience of the people who are in line with the constitution of the Indonesian nation.

Aspects of Pancasila Ideology: by instilling Pancasila values and applying anti-corruption education in any environment in the community. The government, law enforcement, and the community also need to be active in creating Indonesia as a corruption-free place that supports the spirit of the nation's progress with the aspiration to be free from corruption.

SUGGESTION

An anti-corruption education study can be carried out with a positivistic approach to evaluate the achievements of perceptions about the anti-corruption movement. People already know that corruption is bad, sinful, harmful to others, but there are still many who violate it. This is as evidence of awareness and action to be in harmony.

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